

CHARTS FOR A COMPUTATION OF THE COHOMOLOGY OF \mathbb{R} -MOTIVIC $\mathcal{A}(2)$

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ABSTRACT. This document describes the structure of some charts used in a computation of the cohomology of \mathbb{R} -motivic $\mathcal{A}(2)$ via the ρ -Bockstein spectral sequence.

This document describes the structure of some charts regarding the authors computation of the cohomology of \mathbb{R} -motivic $\mathcal{A}(2)$, defined as $\text{Ext}_{\mathcal{A}(2)}^{s,f,w}(\mathbb{M}_2, \mathbb{M}_2)$. These charts are meant to accompany the article [Emm25].

For more mathematical detail, see the cited article. The rest of this document describes the structure of the charts. These descriptions agree with [Emm25, Section 4].

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1. CHARTS

1.1. **Generalities.** The following properties hold true for all charts:

- The horizontal axis describes the stem s ,
- the vertical axis describes the Adams filtration f .

Consequently, we have to plot τ -multiples implicitly since τ has both stem and Adams filtration equal to 0. Most often, we do the following:

- Colors indicate behavior with respect to τ -multiplication. The exact meaning of each color depends on the individual chart and is discussed in the sections below.

Another important element is ρ . For structural reasons, we do the following:

- We try to avoid plotting ρ -multiples whenever possible.

As a consequence, the only charts where ρ -multiples are plotted explicitly are the ρ -power-torsion charts and the charts for the ρ -free quotient of the cohomology of $\mathcal{A}(2)$.

For each chart there are two versions available: A pdf version and an html version. The html version always provides more information. Hovering over a dot in an html chart shows its name, degrees and other data. In particular, we can quickly find the weight of an element in the chart, assuming we know its stem and Adams filtration. The drawback of the html charts is that the name of each element is not directly printed onto the chart, so it might be harder to find a desired element at first glance. The pdf version has the name of each element¹ printed on the chart. That can make it easier to find a desired element, as long as there aren't too many elements in the same stem and Adams filtration. In summary, the pdf charts are simpler to use when unfamiliar with the names of elements and their degrees, but the html charts are a more efficient tool because the weights are integral to our computation. Ultimately, which version to use depends on the specific chart and personal preference.

We will now give detailed instructions on how to read each set of charts.

1.2. **Cohomology of $\mathcal{A}(2)$ ρ -localized.** This chart shows the ρ -localization of the cohomology of \mathbb{R} -motivic $\mathcal{A}(2)$. It contains the following information:

- A dot represents the module $\mathbb{F}_2[\rho^{\pm 1}, \tau^8]$,
- lines of slope 1 represent h_1 -multiplication, lines of slope 1/3 represent h_2 -multiplication,
- an arrow of slope 1 indicates that a given dot supports infinitely many h_1 -multiplications.

1.3. **ρ -Bockstein E_r -pages ρ -free quotient.** The ρ -free quotient of the E_r -page is defined to be $E_r/(\rho\text{-power-torsion})$. Since every element in this quotient is ρ -torsion free, we leave out all ρ -multiples in the charts.

Generally, the following will hold true for all pages:

- Dots represent a quotient of $\mathbb{F}_2[\rho, \tau^n]$, where the power n depends on the page,
- the color of a dot determines the τ^n -torsion of that quotient,
- vertical lines represent h_0 -multiplication, lines of slope 1 represent h_1 -multiplication, lines of slope 1/3 represent h_2 -multiplication,
- the color of a line simply corresponds to the color of its target dot, except when the line is colored magenta², which indicates that the given multiplication hits the τ^n -multiple of the target dot,

¹Except for h_0 -, h_1 -, and h_2 -multiples, but the fact that they are multiples is typically visualized by a line in the chart so their name can be inferred easily from the dot that they are connected to via that line.

²Here is an example of what a magenta line looks like.

- two lines originating from the same dot implies that the h_i -multiplication in question hits the sum of those two targets,
- arrows indicate that a given dot supports infinitely many multiplications of the type corresponding to the slope of the arrow, e.g. a vertical arrow indicates infinitely many h_0 -multiples, an arrow of slope 1 indicates infinitely many h_1 -multiples,
- the color of an arrow indicates the τ^n -torsion of the implied multiples.

1.3.1. E_1 . We provide a table on how to interpret the colors in this chart.

Table 1: Colors for the ρ -Bockstein E_1 -page ρ -free quotient

Color	Example	Module
gray	•	$\mathbb{F}_2[\rho, \tau]$
red	•	$\mathbb{F}_2[\rho, \tau]/\tau$
blue	•	$\mathbb{F}_2[\rho, \tau]/\tau^2$
green	•	$\mathbb{F}_2[\rho, \tau]/\tau^3$

1.3.2. E_2 . We provide a table on how to interpret the colors in this chart. A magenta line now indicates that the corresponding multiplication hits the τ^2 -multiple of the target dot.

Table 2: Colors for the ρ -Bockstein E_2 -page ρ -free quotient

Color	Example	Module
gray	•	$\mathbb{F}_2[\rho, \tau^2]$
red	•	$\mathbb{F}_2[\rho, \tau^2]/\tau^2$
blue	•	$\mathbb{F}_2[\rho, \tau^2]/(\tau^2)^2$

1.3.3. E_3 and E_4 . We provide a table on how to interpret the colors in this chart. A magenta line now indicates that the corresponding multiplication hits the τ^4 -multiple of the target dot.

Table 3: Colors for the ρ -Bockstein E_3 -page and E_4 -page ρ -free quotient

Color	Example	Module
gray	•	$\mathbb{F}_2[\rho, \tau^4]$
red	•	$\mathbb{F}_2[\rho, \tau^4]/\tau^4$

1.3.4. E_r for $r \geq 5$. We provide a table on how to interpret the colors in this chart.

Table 4: Colors for the ρ -Bockstein E_r -page ρ -free quotient, $r \geq 5$

Color	Example	Module
gray	•	$\mathbb{F}_2[\rho, \tau^8]$
red	•	$\mathbb{F}_2[\rho, \tau^8]/\tau^8$

1.4. **ρ -Bockstein internal coweight charts.** The internal coweight is defined as $s + f - w$. We provide charts for fixed values of the internal coweight on various E_r -page ρ -free quotients.

The charts contain the following information:

- A dot represents the module $\mathbb{F}_2[\rho]$,
- the color of a dot follows the coloring scheme of the respective E_r -page the chart is based on,³
- an arrow pointing to the left indicates that the given dot is not involved in any differentials, i.e. it represents a ρ -torsion free class on E_∞ ,
- a cyan line⁴ connecting two dots indicates a ρ -Bockstein differential. The length of the line (or equivalently the relative position of the two dots it connects) implies which page the differential occurs on. More precisely, a line of slope $1/(r-1)$ represents a d_r -differential from the dot in lower Adams filtration to the ρ^r -multiple of the dot in higher Adams filtration.

Some charts show all differentials and some charts do not show differentials.

1.5. Cohomology of $\mathcal{A}(2)$ ρ -free quotient. We provide two charts which combine into the ρ -free quotient of the cohomology of \mathbb{R} -motivic $\mathcal{A}(2)$, i.e. $\text{Ext}_{\mathcal{A}(2)}(\mathbb{M}_2, \mathbb{M}_2)/(\rho\text{-power-torsion})$. The first chart shows elements of coweight $s-w$ congruent to 0, 1, and 2 mod 8. The second chart shows elements of coweight congruent to 4 mod 8. In particular, there are no ρ -torsion free elements in other coweights.

The charts contain the following information:

- A dot represents the module $\mathbb{F}_2[\tau^8]$,
- lines of slope 1 represent h_1 -multiplication, lines of slope $1/3$ represent h_2 -multiplication, horizontal lines represent ρ -multiplication,
- horizontal arrows indicate that a given dot supports infinitely many ρ -multiplications,
- dotted lines indicate that a multiplication comes from a hidden extension,
- magenta lines indicate that a multiplication hits the τ^8 -multiple of the target dot. All magenta lines are consequences of hidden τ^8 -extensions.

There are multiplications that are not hidden on the generator of a dot itself, but on the τ^8 -multiple of that generator. We have chosen not to introduce a separate symbol for this phenomenon, and simply draw a solid line.

1.6. ρ -Bockstein E_∞ -page ρ -power-torsion. There are eight charts combining into the ρ -power-torsion subalgebra of the E_∞ -page of the ρ -Bockstein spectral sequence. The charts are divided into coweights $s-w$ mod 8. These charts do not show any hidden extensions.

The charts contain the following information:

- A dot represents a quotient of $\mathbb{F}_2[\tau^8]$,
- the color of a dot determines the τ^8 -torsion of that quotient, see table 5,
- vertical lines represent h_0 -multiplication, lines of slope 1 represent h_1 -multiplication, lines of slope $1/3$ represent h_2 -multiplication, horizontal lines represent ρ -multiplication,
- the color of a line simply corresponds to the color of its target dot,
- arrows indicate that a given dot supports infinitely many multiplications of the type corresponding to the slope of the arrow,
- the color of an arrow indicates the τ^8 -torsion of the implied multiples.

³But it should be noted that a dot does not represent any τ^n -multiples here, as τ^n does not have internal coweight 0.

⁴Here is an example of what a cyan line looks like.

Table 5: Colors for the ρ -Bockstein E_∞ -page ρ -power-torsion

Color	Example	Module
gray	•	$\mathbb{F}_2[\tau^8]$
red	•	$\mathbb{F}_2[\tau^8]/\tau^8$

REFERENCES

[Emm25] Konstantin Emming. The cohomology of \mathbb{R} -motivic $\mathcal{A}(2)$. preprint, 2025.

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